

USING NON-STANDARD TESTS IN TEACHING

"MAHBUB UL-QULUB"

Egamberdiyeva Zilola Alimbayevna

Master's student of Urgench State University

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These test tasks allow students to monitor and evaluate not only their acquired knowledge but also their skills in recognizing objects and their parts, and identifying their unique characteristics.

ABSTRACT

When monitoring the achievement of the cognitive educational goal by students, it is advisable to determine the level of assimilation by them of information and data on the topic of prose and poetic excerpts from the work "Mahbub ul-qulub." For this, the student must identify objects related to the topic, define them, process information, express their opinion, explain the essence of a particular process, object, or event, and highlight the specific characteristics of this process, object, or event.

When monitoring the achievement of the cognitive educational goal by students, it is advisable to determine the level of assimilation by them of information and data on the topic of prose and poetic excerpts from the work "Mahbub ul-qulub." For this, the student must identify objects related to the topic, define them, process information, express their opinion, explain the essence of a particular process, object, or event, and highlight the specific characteristics of this process, object, or event. When determining the level of achievement of the educational goal of knowledge, it is recommended to use the following non-standard tests with multiple answers. These test tasks allow students to monitor and evaluate not only their acquired knowledge but also their skills in recognizing objects and their parts, and identifying their unique characteristics.

1. Determine the order of the thoughts given in each chapter and the bayts given as their interpretation, and write the alternatives of each prose and poetic work in the table.

Multiple answer non-standard test answer

To the people of Dabiristan

"About Medicine

"Regarding Secretaries"

2. Analyze and write in the table below Alisher Navoi's fards and the ideas put forward in them.

FARDS	IDEA
<i>Who taught you a letter in the path of truth, A hundred treasures cannot repay his right</i>	
<i>A skilled physician is a cure for bodily ailments. It's a curse to the ignorant, gloomy, and greedy soul.</i>	
<i>This is the work of wisdom and intelligence, this is salary and game, Where can any egoist and selfish person find this?</i>	

<i>Which scribe would write contrary to that word, May that dark-faced one's head be as thin as a pen To speak of the people's faults, someone extends their tongue. Know that the tongue stretches long enough to expose its own faults</i>	
<i>One has so many skills, the other has so many piles, The wise know best which one is better.</i>	
<i>This is the work of wisdom and intelligence, this is salary and game, Where can any egoist and selfish person find this?</i>	
<i>After this, the Almighty has died, Sheikh-ul-Islam Pir Ansari.</i>	

Non-standard test tasks used to monitor and assess the achievement of students' learning objectives related to understanding

Understanding plays a crucial role within learning objectives. To achieve this educational goal, students must find solutions to the problems studied on the topic of stories in the work "Mahbub ul-qulub," understand their significance, and highlight the main idea. When determining, monitoring, and evaluating the degree to which students have achieved this educational goal, it is required that they summarize the ideas contained in the educational material, process the main idea, provide examples, express their opinion, and defend it. These levels can only be determined using multi-answer non-standard test tasks.

The practical application of students' knowledge of Bloom's taxonomy requires students to process, adapt, and retell the educational material in the process of completing tasks that involve applying the acquired theoretical knowledge in a new unexpected situation using non-standard test tasks used to control and assess the level of achievement of the educational goal.

The level of achievement of the educational goal of applying the acquired theoretical knowledge of students in practice can be determined using the following multi-answer, tabular non-standard test tasks.

Which of the following statements is true?

1. In Navoi's works, along with verbal arts, spiritual arts are skillfully used in their place.
2. In his works, Navoi cited parables in order to prove and substantiate his thoughts.
3. If we analyze Navoi's fards from an artistic point of view, we see in them the perfection of figurative expression, high artistic skill, and poetic beauty.

If the given statements are true, "yes" is written; if they are false, "no" is written.

1. In Navoi's works, along with verbal arts, spiritual arts were also skillfully used in their proper place. (yes)
2. In the works of Navoi, in order to prove and substantiate his thoughts, he cited parables. (yes)
3. If we analyze Navoi's fards from an artistic point of view, we see in them the perfection of figurative expression, high artistic skill, and poetic beauty. (yes)

Write down the omitted words.

1. Who does not show loyalty to anyone, Shohli'g' tarkiga _____.
2. In the midst of ____,

The snake is between two dragons.

3. With non-breeding property _____,

I don't want to _____.

Write down the missing words (answer)

1. Who does not show loyalty to anyone,

He will not renounce the kingdom.

2. His soul is between two calamities,

Mor is between two dragons.

3. Without looking towards the kingdom and army,

Without inclining towards the pleader.

Non-standard test tasks used to synthesize students' knowledge of Bloom's taxonomy, to monitor and evaluate the level of achievement of the learning objective

Within the framework of learning objectives, the synthesis of knowledge occupies an important place. The main essence of the synthesis learning objective is for students to embody the main ideas within the course or topic, grouping, generalizing, or reconstructing them based on the specific characteristics of the processes and objects. These mental operations, which should be performed by students, are performed using non-standard tests with multiple answers.

Non-standard test tasks used to monitor and evaluate the level of achievement of students' learning objectives related to drawing conclusions

Within the framework of learning objectives, drawing conclusions serves as a concluding and system-forming function. The main essence of the learning objective of summarizing is to summarize the course or topic studied by students. In this process, students are required to evaluate the information contained in the educational content, express an opinion against the opinion, support or refute it, using critical thinking skills. In this process, non-standard multi-answer test tasks are used.